

UNDERSTANDING *PHILAENUS SPUMARIUS* BEHAVIOR AND HOSTS PREFERENCE FOR PREDICTING *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* SPREAD UNDER CENTRAL-EUROPEAN CONDITIONS

A. MARKHEISER^{1*}, D. CORNARA², A. FERERES², M. MAIXNER¹

¹JULIUS KÜHN-INSTITUT (JKI), INSTITUTE FOR PLANT PROTECTION IN FRUIT CROPS AND VITICULTURE, SIEBELDINGEN, GERMANY. ²INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS AGRARIAS, CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, ICA-CSIC, MADRID, SPAIN.

***Corresponding author: anna.markheiser@julius-kuehn.de**

Within Europe, the meadow spittlebug *Philaenus spumarius* is the only epidemiologically relevant vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* identified so far, playing a key role in bacterial transmission to olive in South Italy. However, considering its large host range and wide distribution, the spittlebug could be a relevant vector across all the outbreaks detected in Europe by now. In 2016, a single oleander plant infected with *X. fastidiosa* ssp. 'fastidiosa' was spotted in Germany; the plant was destroyed and the outbreak is nowadays considered eradicated. Nevertheless, the finding prompted a survey aimed at characterizing candidate vectors presence, biology and ecology.

A previous study in Southwest Germany already confirmed the occurrence of *P. spumarius*, *Neophilaenus campestris* and 12 other potential vector species belonging to the families Aphrophoridae (5 species), Cercopidae (3 species) and Cicadellidae: Cicadellinae (4 species). The survey focused especially on the xylem-feeder community in areas like gardens/parks, the most likely pathway of the bacterium into Germany, wherefrom it could be spread to adjoined areas like vineyards and cherry orchards. Indeed, *X. fastidiosa* could be introduced through ornamental plants, such as rosemary and oleander, being subsequently transmitted to cultivated plants, like grapevine and cherry, by polyphagous vectors as *P. spumarius*.

Therefore, in order to infer possible pathways of spread of *X. fastidiosa* in case of a large-scale introduction of the bacterium in Germany, we carried out several experiments to gather epidemiologically essential data on *P. spumarius* feeding behaviour and host plant choice/suitability. The probing and feeding activities of adult *P. spumarius* on rosemary, oleander, cherry and grapevine were analyzed by EPG (Electrical Penetration Graph). Furthermore, we conducted observations on host plant acceptance and settlement behavior through choice and no-choice tests under controlled conditions. Additionally, the phenology and host plant shifting under field conditions were observed in vineyards and cherry orchards within two winegrowing-regions in Germany ('Mosel' and 'Palatinate'). Overall, the data of this multidisciplinary project furnish important and urgently required indications on the potential risk posed by *P. spumarius* for the establishment and spread of *X. fastidiosa* under Central-European conditions.